

Sacred Skills and Silent Knowledge: Communicating East Sumba Ikat Weaving Heritage through a Transactive Memory Perspective

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Abstract

Background: There are barriers to access to knowledge of Ikat weaving among East Sumba Ikat weaving artisans, which hinder the communication of the inheritance of East Sumba Ikat weaving.

Objectives: This study aims to analyse access to knowledge in the inheritance of Ikat weaving in the East Sumba Ikat weaving artisan group.

Method: This research employs a phenomenological approach, with informants being East Sumba Ikat weavers who have worked in the field for years.

Results: There are three categories of access to Ikat weaving knowledge: open, limited, and closed. Closed knowledge is a stage of knowledge that is difficult to access and communicate due to cultural boundaries. In the context of Transactive memory, this closed knowledge hinders the retrieval of Ikat weaving knowledge, thereby threatening the transmission of Ikat weaving among artisans.

Conclusion: This study concludes that communication about inheritance is problematic because not all knowledge of Ikat weaving is freely accessible. Knowledge at certain stages is traditionally restricted, limiting artisans' ability to master it. As a result, the inheritance process of Ikat weaving occurs partially at certain stages only, not at all stages of making Ikat weaving.

Unique Contribution: This study identifies communication issues in the inheritance of intangible assets within informal groups that remain bound by specific traditional rules. In

addition, this study contributes to the development of Transactive memory theory for informal groups influenced by cultural factors.

Key Recommendation: Communication regarding the inheritance of intangible assets, such as Ikat weaving, should consider cultural values to ensure that the solutions offered are relevant to the cultural context adopted by cultural actors.

Keywords: Ikat weaving, Communication, Knowledge, Transactive memory, East Sumba

Introduction

Indonesia is a country rich in intangible heritage. UNESCO defines intangible heritage as a tradition or living expression of ancestral heritage passed down from generation to generation, including knowledge and practices related to nature, as well as knowledge and skills for producing traditional handicraft products. One of the intangible heritage items in Indonesia that warrants attention due to its challenging preservation is East Sumba Ikat weaving. East Sumba Ikat weaving has three main functions: social, cultural, and economic (Kartiwa, 1989; Ndima, 2007). The social function is as everyday clothing and also souvenirs for guests or relatives; the cultural function where weaving is an important identity/symbol in ritual ceremonies related to funerals and marriages (Adams, 1969; Adams et al., 1999; Ajayi, 2023; Ndima, 2007), and; economic function where woven fabrics become commodities that can be sold (Lolo, 2018; Ndima, 2007). The uniqueness of East Sumba Ikat weaving is also due to the complexity of the ikat weaving process, which involves dozens of steps (Prijosusilo, 2017). Therefore, Sumbanese Ikat weaving represents Indonesia's weaving tradition (Setiawan & Suwarnigdyah, 2014). Another note, summarized by the Indonesian Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology in 2023, regarding Ikat weaving states that the Sumbanese Ikat weaving motif is one of the most numerous motifs in Indonesia, with a total of 85 recorded motifs, 16 of which are threatened with extinction because there are no more artisans. The number of Ikat weaving artisans recorded through 2022 was 476, yet only 19 were Ikat weaving maestros. The weaving maestros, whose numbers are declining, are understood as artisans who not only weave but also understand the values and philosophies inherent in weaving. In contrast, most Ikat weaving artisans produce weaving solely as a cultural product. Scrase reported similar findings: in Indonesia, modernization in the traditional textile industry has led to unemployment among more than 400,000 traditional ikat weaving artisans, particularly in the dyeing sector (Dias et al., 2020; Scrase, 2003). The decreasing number of them threatens the inheritance of Ikat weaving (Buckley, 2016).

Based on the Ikat weaving process, there are dozens of steps that must be completed by weaving artisans, from selecting the thread to producing the Ikat (Prijosusilo, 2017). Of the dozens of steps, at least one can be categorized into six main stages of East Sumba Ikat weaving: thread arrangement, pattern making, blue colouring, red colouring, weaving, and locking the thread ends (Hana et al., 2025). The stages of Ikat weaving must be carried out sequentially. One artisan cannot accomplish it; it requires several artisans to form a group. Each artisan has distinct skills across the weaving stages, which, when combined, produce Ikat works. This phenomenon illustrates that Ikat weaving is a group-based cultural practice, in which each member specializes in specific stages. No artisan masters all stages of making Ikat weaving. Each artisan passes on knowledge only at the stages they have mastered. Specific knowledge is not freely shared among artisans because of myths and cultural boundaries believed to thwart Ikat weaving if violated.

Based on this description, group memory does not appear to develop because not all knowledge can be accessed together within the group. Information that should be accessible and communicated as shared knowledge for group purposes is only owned by certain group members. Previous research indicates that a lack of communication reduces the accuracy of identifying group members' expertise, thereby disrupting knowledge transfer through interpersonal communication within the group (Su, 2021). Knowledge transfer within this informal Ikat weaving group is relevant to the study of Transactive memory in a formal group. However, the three Transactive memory processes in formal groups, directory updating, information allocation, and retrieval coordination, are carried out through a clear structure and hierarchy. This process differs from that in informal Ikat weaving groups, where cultural norms contribute to Transactive memory. Retention of knowledge at certain stages inhibits Transactive memory and results in the inheritance of Ikat weaving among artisans.

Objectives of the study

This study aims to analyse access to Ikat weaving knowledge in communicating Ikat weaving inheritance, using the concept of Transactive memory among East Sumba Ikat weaving artisans.

Theoretical Framework

To understand the communication context in which artisans share and access knowledge, researchers draw on the theory of Transactive memory. The theory of Transactive memory explains how individuals can access knowledge stored in others' memories through communication (Wegner, 1987). The theory of Transactive memory emphasizes the role of communication in connecting individual memory systems in a group. Through interaction and information exchange, individuals not only store knowledge personally but also rely on collective memories formed within their social networks. Thus, communication is the primary mechanism that enables access to, utilisation of, and coordination of knowledge shared among group members (Hollingshead, 1998; Hollingshead et al., 2011; Palazzolo, 2011; Wegner et al., 1985). Transactive memory occurs when individuals can support their memory by using others as memory aids. Individuals are responsible for obtaining the information needed to complete their respective tasks in developing a Transactive memory system within a group. Each individual remembers their share of the information; they also know who knows what and whom they can ask for that information. This approach yields cognitive benefits for group members by reducing the need to remember everything.

There are two main benefits for teams in developing Transactive memory systems (Palazzolo, 2011): First, each member's cognitive load is reduced. The reduction in cognitive load occurs because team members only need to master information in a limited number of knowledge domains. This condition allows them to delve deeper into their respective areas of specialization. Consequently, they are not burdened by the need to learn information outside their areas of expertise. The second benefit is the team's increased collective capacity to store and access knowledge. By focusing on the domains that best suit their capacities, each member tends to gain a deeper understanding than if they had to master all knowledge simultaneously. Thus, the team builds a broader knowledge base as each individual develops knowledge in a more specific domain. Through effective communication mechanisms, team members can access and utilize this collective knowledge as needed, increasing efficiency in completing tasks.

Transactive memory theory introduces three key concepts to explain how communication can facilitate the development of Transactive memory (Hollingshead & Brandon, 2003; Littlejohn et al., 2021). *First*, groups need to create a directory update. Directory updates identify who knows what in the group and are continually refined as new information is discovered. Group members can also use third parties to build knowledge or ask each other about their skills and expertise. *Second*, groups need to determine effective information allocation strategies—who gets to share what information. For example, during an interaction, members may discover that none of them know anything about a piece of important information in the group. In this case, the group might agree to designate one person to take primary responsibility for learning the information. *Third*, the group needs to engage in coordinated retrieval. Retrieval means reconnecting the knowledge held by each group member to achieve the group's goals. For members to use information in the group, they need to remember who has it and stimulate their memory for it. Although Transactive retrieval can involve simple recognition and recall, it can also result in something new—a shared interpretation of the information. For example, as the group discusses the possible solutions to a group problem that will be used, members may realize that there are benefits to using a combination of solutions rather than just one solution. From this explanation, proper communication plays a role in facilitating the development of Transactive memory in groups. Communication problems often arise because communication can result in poor memory of information; for example, groups rely on one person because that person seems to be an expert in everything, and group members do not share everything they know because they feel there is a personal advantage in withholding information. Group conflict inhibits effective information sharing (Hollingshead et al., 2011).

Methodology

This study uses a phenomenological method, with informants from East Sumba Ikat weaving artisans who have worked as Ikat weaving artisans for years. The informants, comprising both men and women with diverse expertise across the stages of Ikat production, have incorporated weaving into their family livelihoods for generations. In addition, these artisans also still practice weaving using a natural process. The natural Ikat weaving technique still applies the weaving stages more completely, so that the role of group members in sharing knowledge can be identified more precisely, following the study's objectives.

Results

East Sumba Ikat weaving consists of more than 40 steps, from providing yarn to creating woven fabric ready to be marketed. The long process is summarized in six main stages related to the knowledge of Ikat weaving artisans, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Main Stages of East Sumba Ikat Weaving Process

Two East Sumba Ikat weaving types are blue (*Hinggi Kawuru*) and Red (*Hinggi Kombu*). For the manufacture of blue Ikat weaving, stage 4 is not necessary, so the manufacture of Ikat

weaving is shorter, namely 4-6 months. On the other hand, red ikat weaving can take one to a year because it must go through all the stages above. The artisans' access to knowledge at the stages of making Ikat weaving is explained in the table. 1 as follows:

Table 1. Main stages and knowledge accessibility of East Sumba Ikat weaving

Main Stages of Making Ikat Weaving	Knowledge Accessibility
Thread arrangement	Open Knowledge
Pattern Making	Limited Knowledge
Blue dyeing	Closed Knowledge
Red dyeing	Open Knowledge
Weaving	Limited Knowledge
Thread locking	Limited Knowledge

Source: Authors, 2025

The study results showed that the Ikat weaving artisans had different knowledge - it could even be said that there was a reasonably large gap in knowledge between one artisan and another in the six stages above. As a result, differences in expertise led to an unbalanced dependency between artisans. The tricky part of making Ikat weaving was only mastered by a few artisans, and not infrequently, these artisans were separated by quite a distance. The artisans said that they were constrained by knowledge at various stages. Access to this knowledge was not always easy, even if they wanted to learn. According to this research, access to Ikat weaving knowledge is divided into open, limited, and closed knowledge.

Open knowledge in the stages of making Ikat weaving

Open knowledge in making Ikat weaving refers to the knowledge of artisans that is easily accessible and can be shared with other artisans. The main characteristics of this knowledge are that it is general, freely accessible, can be done by all artisans, can be done in open spaces, and there are no cultural taboos. On the other hand, the work steps are easy, the work results are predictable, and the knowledge is freely disseminated. The stages included in this category are the thread arrangement and red dyeing stages, as shown in Figures 2 and 3 below.

Figure 2. Thread arrangement stage

Figure 3. Red dyeing stage

Limited knowledge in the stages of making Ikat weaving

The type of limited knowledge referred to is knowledge of Ikat weaving, which can be accessed, but to master this knowledge, artisans need certain efforts. The efforts require technical expertise, time dedication, and a high interest in learning. In addition, the limited nature also means that not all artisans can work at this stage due to traditional constraints. This situation means certain artisans cannot work at this stage, even though the knowledge can be accessed. Therefore, because of the limited knowledge, not all artisans can work on Ikat weaving at the intended stage. The next is the limitation due to location. Specific knowledge can be accessed, but other artisans have difficulty teaching it because it is centralized in a particular location. Based on this description, the types of limited knowledge in making Ikat weaving are pattern making, weaving, and thread locking stages.

In the pattern-making stage, artisans must at least have mathematical and conceptual imagination so that the patterns formed can have proportional sizes and meaningful structures (Figure 4). Imagination about the patterns, motifs, and colors that will be produced must also be typical of the Sumba tribe and must not conflict with existing traditions. For example, in one of the Ikat weaving centre areas, there must be no horse and chicken patterns on the woven

fabrics, even though the Sumbanese people often keep these two types of animals. This is because the area is believed to have been passed down from generation to generation as the place where the ancestors of the Sumbanese first arrived, and the sacredness of horses and chickens is evident in various traditional Sumbanese rituals. Limitations such as these increasingly highlight the uniqueness of Ikat weaving patterns in specific centers, which artisans must master. Furthermore, other traditional limitations, namely at the weaving and locking stages of the thread ends, are stages that, although accessible, must not be carried out by male ikat weaving artisans. The local community believes that men who work in these stages will not have children or will suffer from incurable diseases. Therefore, referring to Figure 1, the stages of Ikat weaving that male artisans can do are only at stages 1-4. This finding indicates that, within local cultural norms, female ikat weaving artisans have broader access to work on all stages of Ikat weaving (stages 1-6). The next limited knowledge is that the final stage, namely locking the ends of the thread, is performed only at one location. Unlike stages 1-5, which can be found in all East Sumba Ikat weaving centers, the end locking stage has been passed down from generation to generation only in a small village in one of the Ikat weaving centers. As a result, artisans in residents' houses work on the end-locking stage of the thread, distinct from other Ikat weaving centre areas in East Sumba. This phenomenon indicates that location also hinders access to knowledge of Ikat weaving among East Sumba Ikat artisans. The stages of making Ikat weaving, which are categorized as limited knowledge, are shown in the three figures presented sequentially below.

Figure 4. Pattern-making stage

Figure 5. Weaving stage

Figure 6. Thread locking stage

Closed knowledge in the stages of making Ikat weaving

Closed knowledge in the context of Ikat weaving is a type of knowledge that should not be shared freely, is rife with myths, and carries a high risk of failure. Therefore, very few artisans have this knowledge. If, at other stages, artisans find it easier to access their knowledge, or knowledge can be mastered, as long as there is a firm intention to learn a specific technique, this is not the case with the blue colouring stage, which is classified as closed knowledge and is highly secretive. Because it is highly secret, many artisans who lack this knowledge are willing to invest time, energy, and even money in working with those who possess it. One reason the blue colouring stage is difficult and cannot be learned independently is that this knowledge is passed down within a narrow circle of the family. This fact leaves artisans from families that have not mastered the art of making blue with almost no opportunity to acquire this knowledge. Another reason Ikat weaving artisans cannot learn the blue colour stage is the belief that only talented individuals are worthy of acquiring this knowledge. Even biological children, if they are considered not to have the talent to work on the blue colouring stage, will not be shared with biological children. The artisans use a traditional testing procedure believed to determine whether an individual is talented at performing this stage (Figure 7). This phenomenon of knowledge hiding further narrows access to knowledge for other artisans, especially outside the family environment.

Figure 7. Blue hands as a sign of talent in mastering the blue dyeing stage

In addition to talent, artisans typically create a dedicated room for blue dyeing to preserve the process's exclusivity. The room must be closed and can only be entered by artisans who can work on these stages. In addition to being closed, this room must be placed where people rarely pass. Even family members not involved in making the blue colour are not allowed to enter the room. The artisans believe the blue dyeing process will fail if this prohibition is violated.

Failure is defined as the entire process being considered a failure over months, and not producing Ikat weaving. Working in this closed room clearly illustrates how knowledge of how to make blue colour is inaccessible.

A characteristic of the blue dyeing stage is that many myths surround it. The most common myth in the blue dyeing stage is that women who are pregnant or menstruating should not be involved in the blue dyeing process because it will thwart the ongoing process. Likewise, people working at this stage should not respond to others' greetings while working. These myths are believed to influence the success or failure of making Ikat weaving. Several informants reported failures that resulted in significant losses. This condition made them very careful, avoiding existing taboos and tending to hide all knowledge related to this stage. These facts render access to knowledge arduous at this stage, and the number of artisans remains limited. The scarcity of knowledge at the blue colour stage is also evidenced by the absence of any artisans who master this stage at one of the Ikat weaving centers in East Sumba. Therefore, artisans in the area must travel considerable distances to complete the construction of the blue stage.

Discussion

Based on the results of this study, it appears that the lack of access to knowledge of ikat weaving due to hereditary traditions impedes the inheritance of Ikat weaving. At certain stages, the artisans will be entirely dependent on one another. This situation is relevant to the assumptions underlying Transactive memory theory (Hollingshead, 1998; Hollingshead & Brandon, 2003). The problem of access to knowledge arises because artisans withhold specific knowledge due to cultural norms. As a result, the communication of Ikat weaving knowledge among artisans with different specializations is impeded. The phenomenon of withholding knowledge (Hollingshead et al., 2011) in informal groups of Ikat weaving artisans can be examined through three processes in Transactive memory theory: directory updating, information allocation, and retrieval coordination (Littlejohn et al., 2021; Palazzolo, 2011).

First, in the directory updating process, there is a concept of physical proximity and even blood relations between artisans that allow them to identify who knows what at the stages of Ikat weaving. Moreover, blood relations are required to share knowledge at certain stages of Ikat weaving. In addition to blood relations, location factors that facilitate close communication also contribute to the identification of an artisan's Ikat weaving knowledge (Hana et al., 2025). Based on this identification, artisans can determine with whom to collaborate to address gaps in knowledge and Ikat weaving skills they have not yet mastered. The directory updating process among informal Ikat weaving artisans is undoubtedly different from the directory updating intended in the initial context of the Transactive memory theory in formal groups. Closeness, lineage, and geographical context are characteristics of cooperative relations among Ikat weaving artisans.

Second, the Information allocation process is an effort by Ikat weaving artisans to fill the knowledge gap they have not mastered. Information allocation refers to the division and distribution of knowledge among group members (Wegner, 1987), based on who is considered to know the most or to be responsible for a particular type of knowledge in Ikat weaving. In formal groups, this division of tasks is determined by each member's specialization and proven competencies, as evidenced by education or specialized training. In addition, the distribution of knowledge within formal groups is regulated by group management. This situation does not

arise in Ikat weaving groups, as artisans who also own the woven cloth exercise full control over the production process and organize their working groups according to the scope of specializations they have mastered. The greater the number of weaving stages mastered by these artisan-owners, the lower their dependence on other artisans. The types of knowledge of making Ikat weaving, minimal knowledge, and closed knowledge are distinctive differences in this knowledge allocation process. Depending on culture, not all artisans have equal access to these two types of knowledge. For knowledge limited to pattern-making, only artisans with sustained learning and high creativity can master it. On the other hand, although knowledge of the weaving and thread-locking stages is accessible, it cannot be accessed due to traditional gender constraints. Women have more access than men at both stages above. Customary restrictions that prohibit men from accessing the entire stages of weaving create an unequal Transactive memory structure. Women hold primary authority in knowledge (Adams et al., 1999; Lolo, 2018), whereas men master only some stages. This finding confirms that gender constructions and local cultural norms shape the Transactive memory phenomenon in Sumbanese weaving. Limited access is more pronounced in closed knowledge, where myths as part of the tradition surrounding Ikat weaving constrain the distribution of knowledge among Ikat weaving artisans. Dependence on artisans who possess specialized knowledge arises not because there is no desire to learn from them, but because of cultural constraints. As a result, the most crucial stage in making Ikat weaving, namely blue dyeing, is the most difficult knowledge to allocate. There is a withholding of knowledge at this stage, so artisans with this knowledge are very few. No more artisans have mastered this stage, even in one of the four centers studied. Artisans who possess closed knowledge are not free to share it. Conversely, artisans who are considered untrained or whose families have not mastered this knowledge cannot acquire it freely. Even more extreme, for artisans who master this knowledge but do not have children considered talented to work on the blue dyeing stage, this knowledge will not be transmitted to their biological children, as they are considered unworthy of receiving it.

The third process is the coordination of knowledge retrieval. For this process, open knowledge, namely the stages of thread arrangement and red dyeing, is the knowledge that is easiest to retrieve among Ikat weaving artisans. On the other hand, the type of limited knowledge cannot be readily retrieved within a group of artisans because it is tacit and undocumented. Tacit knowledge requires experience-based interactions that develop relationally, not informationally. Without intimate relationships and shared spaces of practice, tacit knowledge will never enter the collective memory of a group. This suggests that the concept of knowledge sharing in Transactive memory is inadequate for tacit knowledge, particularly within cultural communities. However, its open nature to limited knowledge can provide learning opportunities for Ikat weaving artisans who intend to learn the stages of limited knowledge. Thus, maintaining continuity at both the open and limited stages requires consistent corrective communication that enables the exchange of experience without violating customary norms, ensuring that knowledge continues to circulate without disrupting the existing social structure. Compared to these two types of knowledge, namely open and limited knowledge, the retrieval process is the most difficult to occur in closed knowledge, where closed knowledge cannot be shared freely. Artisans' belief from generation to generation about the sacredness of the blue stage, which is closed in nature, is only worthy of being worked on by certain artisans who are considered talented. This condition makes the retrieval process difficult to occur in blue-stage knowledge. The deadlock in retrieving real knowledge is seen when certain stages are carried out in closed rooms that are considered sacred. This condition ultimately produces excessive dependence on specific members and constrains collective knowledge retrieval, thereby

contradicting the foundational assumptions of Transactive memory theory regarding shared access to distributed expertise within groups (Su, 2021). A direct consequence of this situation is that the economic function of woven cloth is also hampered by the obstruction of knowledge at this stage, which slows down Ikat production (Buckley, 2016; Scrase, 2003). Therefore, in the context of Ikat weaving inheritance, the type of blue stage knowledge is the most difficult to inherit.

Regarding these three processes of Transactive memory, although artisans are aware of who holds expertise in specific stages (directory updating), the processes of information allocation and retrieval coordination are constrained by cultural factors such as gender norms, myths, and perceived innate talent. These limitations lead to partial transmission of knowledge, making the collective memory within Ikat weaving artisan groups only partially functional cognitively. Instead, it is largely shaped and sustained by sociocultural rules that regulate access, authority, and the selective inheritance of skills, resulting in an uneven and culturally bounded collective memory system.

Conclusion

Not all aspects of the inheritance of Ikat weaving knowledge in East Sumba can be fully explained through Transactive memory. Some cultural and social factors show inconsistencies with this theoretical framework. The description of the three Transactive memory processes in informal groups among Ikat weaving artisans indicates that Transactive memory theory needs to be developed to account for tradition. From this Ikat weaving group, it can be concluded that cultural factors play an important role in understanding the phenomenon of limited access to knowledge, which, of course, affects the future of Ikat weaving. Cultural and social factors such as gender, perceptions of innate talent, and lineage, as highlighted in this study, can limit the distribution and transmission of knowledge. This results in collective memory dynamics that differ from those in Transactive memory systems in formal groups, indicating that theoretical adaptations are necessary to reflect local cultural practices accurately.

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